

Some new operations and their properties on q-rung orthopair fuzzy matrices

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Received: 05 Nov 2020

Accepted: 20 Apr 2021

Published Online: 30 Apr 2021

Abstract: In this article, some new operations $[\$, \#, *, \rightarrow]$ of q-rung orthopair fuzzy matrices are defined and discussed several properties. Further, the necessity and possibility operations of q-rung orthopair fuzzy matrices are proved. Finally, we have identified and proved several of these properties, particularly those involving the operation $L \rightarrow M$ defined as q-rung orthopair fuzzy implication with other operations.

Key words: q-rung orthopair fuzzy matrix; Algebraic sum; Algebraic product; Implication operator

1. Introduction

Khan et al. [4] proposed the intuitionistic fuzzy matrices (IFM) $L = [\langle \zeta_{l_{ij}}, \delta_{l_{ij}} \rangle]$, where $\zeta_{l_{ij}} \in [0, 1]$ speak to the participation degree and $\delta_{l_{ij}} \in [0, 1]$ the non-enrollment degree for all i, j , separately. Since the IFM was proposed, it has gotten a great deal of consideration in numerous fields, for example, design acknowledgment, clinical finding, etc. Be that as it may, if the amount of the participation degree and the non-membership degree is more noteworthy than 1, the IFM is not, at this point appropriate. We proposed [13] the Pythagorean fuzzy matrices (PFM) $L = [\langle \zeta_{l_{ij}}, \delta_{l_{ij}} \rangle]$, where the squared amount of its participation degree $\zeta_{l_{ij}} \in [0, 1]$ and nonmembership degree $\delta_{l_{ij}} \in [0, 1]$ is not exactly or equivalent to 1. Since the PFM was raised, it has been broadly applied in various fields, for example, venture dynamic, administration nature of homegrown aircraft, communitarian based recommender frameworks, etc. Despite the fact that the PFM sums up the IFM, it can't portray the accompanying choice data. A board of specialists was welcome to offer their thoughts about the achievability of a speculation plan, and they were partitioned into two autonomous gatherings to settle on a choice. One group considered the degree of the feasibility of the investment plan as 0.8, while the other group considered the nonmembership degree as 0.7. It was clearly seen that $0.8 + 0.7 > 1$, $(0.8)^2 + (0.7)^2 > 1$, and thus it could not be described by IFM and PFM. After the IFM and PFM theory, many researchers attempted the important role in this theory ([1],[2], [5], [6], [7], [9], [10], [11], [12], [14], [15], [16], [17], [18], [19], [20]). To describe such evaluation information, we proposed [21] q-rung orthopair fuzzy matrix (q-ROFM) $L = [\langle \zeta_{l_{ij}}, \delta_{l_{ij}} \rangle]$, where represent the $\zeta_{l_{ij}} \in [0, 1]$ membership degree and $\delta_{l_{ij}} \in [0, 1]$ the non-membership degree for all i, j , respectively, and $0 \leq \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \leq 1$. It was clearly seen that $0.8 + 0.7 > 1$, $(0.8)^2 + (0.7)^2 > 1$, $(0.8)^q + (0.7)^q \leq 1 (q \geq 1)$. Then we defined some q-rung orthopair fuzzy operations $\boxplus_q, \boxtimes_q, @, \cap, \cup$ and properties are considered. This article we have developed some new operations for q-rung orthopair fuzzy matrices and discussed several properties.

2. Some new operations for q-rung orthopair fuzzy matrices

In this section, some existing q-rung orthopair fuzzy operations and we define the new operations for q-rung orthopair fuzzy matrices and investigates the several algebraic properties.

Definition 2.1. [21] **IFM operations on q-ROFM:** Let $F_{m \times n}$ denote the family of all q -ROFMs for all i, j , and let $L, M \in F_{m \times n}$ be given as $L = [\langle \zeta_{l_{ij}}, \delta_{l_{ij}} \rangle]$, $M = [\langle \zeta_{m_{ij}}, \delta_{m_{ij}} \rangle]$.

Some existing q-rung orthopair fuzzy operations:

- (i) $L \vee M = [\langle \max \{ \zeta_{l_{ij}}, \zeta_{m_{ij}} \}, \min \{ \delta_{l_{ij}}, \delta_{m_{ij}} \} \rangle]$
- (ii) $L \wedge M = [\langle \min \{ \zeta_{l_{ij}}, \zeta_{m_{ij}} \}, \max \{ \delta_{l_{ij}}, \delta_{m_{ij}} \} \rangle]$
- (iii) $L^C = [\langle (\delta_{l_{ij}}), (\zeta_{l_{ij}}) \rangle]$
- (iv) $L \boxplus_q M = \left[\left\langle \left(\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q - \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q}, \delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}} \right\rangle \right]$
- (v) $L \boxtimes_q M = \left[\left\langle \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}}, \left(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right]$.
- (vi) $L \textcircled{+} M = \left[\left\langle \left(\frac{\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q}, \left(\frac{\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right]$

We define Some new q-rung orthopair fuzzy operations.

Some new q-rung orthopair fuzzy operations:

- (i) $L \$ M = \left[\left\langle (\zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}})^{1/q}, (\delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}})^{1/q} \right\rangle \right]$,
- (ii) $L \# M = \left[\left\langle \frac{(2)^{1/q} \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}}}{(\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q)^{1/q}}, \frac{(2)^{1/q} \delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}}}{(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q)^{1/q}} \right\rangle \right]$.

For which we shall accept that if $\zeta_{l_{ij}} = \zeta_{m_{ij}} = 0$ then $\frac{\zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}}}{\zeta_{l_{ij}} + \zeta_{m_{ij}}} = 0$ and if $\delta_{l_{ij}} = \delta_{m_{ij}} = 0$, then

$$\frac{\delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}}}{\delta_{l_{ij}} + \delta_{m_{ij}}} = 0.$$

- (iii) $L * M = \left[\left\langle \left(\frac{\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2(\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q + 1)} \right)^{1/q}, \left(\frac{\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q + 1)} \right)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right]$,
- (iv) $L \rightarrow M = [\langle \max \{ \delta_{l_{ij}}, \zeta_{m_{ij}} \}, \min \{ \zeta_{l_{ij}}, \delta_{m_{ij}} \} \rangle]$.

Remark 2.1. Clearly, for each two q-ROFMs A and B , $[(L \textcircled{+} M), (L \$ M), (L \# M), (L * M), (L \rightarrow M)]$ are as yet an q-ROFM. Some basic representations are appear as follows:

For (i),

$$0 \leq \left(\left(\frac{\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q} \right)^q + \left(\left(\frac{\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q} \right)^q = \frac{\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{l_{ij}}^q}{2} + \frac{\zeta_{m_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \leq \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} = 1.$$

For (ii), if $\delta_{l_{ij}} \geq \zeta_{m_{ij}}$ and $\zeta_{l_{ij}} \geq \delta_{m_{ij}}$, then

$$0 \leq \max \{ \delta_{l_{ij}}^q, \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q \} + \min \{ \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q, \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \} \leq \delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q \leq 1.$$

If $\delta_{l_{ij}} \geq \zeta_{m_{ij}}$ and $\zeta_{l_{ij}} \leq \delta_{m_{ij}}$, then

$$0 \leq \max \left\{ \delta_{l_{ij}}^q, \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q \right\} + \min \left\{ \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q, \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right\} \leq \delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q \leq 1.$$

If $\delta_{l_{ij}} \leq \zeta_{m_{ij}}$ and $\zeta_{l_{ij}} \geq \delta_{m_{ij}}$, then

$$0 \leq \max \left\{ \delta_{l_{ij}}^q, \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q \right\} + \min \left\{ \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q, \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right\} \leq \delta_{m_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q \leq 1.$$

If $\delta_{l_{ij}} \leq \zeta_{m_{ij}}$ and $\zeta_{l_{ij}} \leq \delta_{m_{ij}}$, then

$$0 \leq \max \left\{ \delta_{l_{ij}}^q, \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q \right\} + \min \left\{ \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q, \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right\} \leq \delta_{m_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q \leq 1.$$

For (iii),

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &\leq \left((\zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}})^{1/q} \right)^q + \left((\delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}})^{1/q} \right)^q = \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}} + \delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}} = \frac{\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{l_{ij}}^q}{2} + \frac{\zeta_{m_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} = 1. \end{aligned}$$

For (iv),

$$0 \leq \left(\frac{(2)^{1/q} \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}}}{(\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q)^{1/q}} \right)^q + \left(\frac{(2)^{1/q} \delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}}}{(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q)^{1/q}} \right)^q = \frac{2\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q}{\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q} + \frac{2\delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q}{\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q} \leq 1.$$

For (v),

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &\leq \left(\left(\frac{\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2(\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q + 1)} \right)^{1/q} \right)^q + \left(\left(\frac{\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q + 1)} \right)^{1/q} \right)^q \\ &= \frac{\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2(\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q + 1)} \cdot \frac{\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q + 1)} \leq 1. \end{aligned}$$

Lemma 2.1. [5] For any two numbers $r, s \in [0, 1]$, then

$$\begin{aligned} r.s &\leq \min \{r, s\} \leq \frac{2(r.s)}{r+s} \leq \sqrt{r.s} \leq \max \{r, s\} \leq r+s-r.s, \\ r.s &\leq \frac{r+s}{2(r+s+1)} \leq \frac{r+s}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 2.1. For $L, M \in F_{m \times n}$,

- (i) $L \circledast M = M \circledast L = (L^C \circledast M^C)^C$;
- (ii) $L \$ M = M \$ L = (L^C \$ M^C)^C$;
- (iii) $L \# M = M \# L = (L^C \# M^C)^C$;
- (iv) $L * M = M * L = (L^C * M^C)^C$.

Proof. Let (i) is prove, then other can be proved similarly.

(i) Let L and M be two given q-ROFMs, then

$$L \circledast M = \left[\left\langle \left(\frac{\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q}, \left(\frac{\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \left[\left\langle \left(\frac{\zeta_{m_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q}, \left(\frac{\delta_{m_{ij}}^q + \delta_{l_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right], \\
 &= M @ L. \\
 L^C @ M^C &= \left[\left\langle \left(\frac{\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q}, \left(\frac{\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right], \\
 (L^C @ M^C)^C &= \left[\left\langle \left(\frac{\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q}, \left(\frac{\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right] = L @ M.
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $L @ M = L @ M = (L^C @ M^C)^C$. □

The following theorem are obvious.

Theorem 2.2. For $L, M, N \in F_{m \times n}$,

- (i) $(L \wedge M) @ N = (L @ N) \wedge (M @ N)$;
- (ii) $(L \vee M) @ N = (L @ N) \vee (M @ N)$;
- (iii) $(L \wedge M) \$ N = (L \$ N) \wedge (M \$ N)$;
- (iv) $(L \vee M) \$ N = (L \$ N) \vee (M \$ N)$;
- (v) $(L \wedge M) \# N = (L \# N) \wedge (M \# N)$;
- (vi) $(L \vee M) \# N = (L \# N) \vee (M \# N)$;
- (vii) $(L \wedge M) * N = (L * N) \wedge (M * N)$;
- (viii) $(L \vee M) * N = (L * N) \vee (M * N)$.

3. Some results on necessity and possibility operations

In this section, we prove the necessity and possibility operations of q-rung orthopair fuzzy matrices. Then we compile some relevant properties of these operations are discussed.

Definition 3.1. [11] The necessity and possibility operations on a q-rung orthopair fuzzy matrix L is denoted

$$\text{by } \square L, \diamond L \text{ and is } \square L = \left[\left\langle \zeta_{l_{ij}}, \left(1 - \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right], \diamond L = \left[\left\langle \left(1 - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q}, \delta_{l_{ij}} \right\rangle \right].$$

Theorem 3.1. For $L, M \in F_{m \times n}$,

- (i) $\square L @ \square M = \square (L @ M) \leq \diamond L @ \diamond M = \diamond (L @ M)$;
- (ii) $\square (L \$ M) \leq \square L \$ \square M \leq \diamond L \$ \diamond M \leq \diamond (L \$ M)$;
- (iii) $\square (L \# M) \leq \square L \# \square M \leq \diamond L \# \diamond M \leq \diamond (L \# M)$;
- (iv) $\square (L * M) \leq \square L * \square M \leq \diamond L * \diamond M \leq \diamond (L * M)$.

Proof. Let (i) and (iii) are proved, then other can be proved similarly.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{(i) } \square L @ \square M &= \left[\left\langle \left(\frac{\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q}, \left(\frac{1 - \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + 1 - \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right] = \square (L @ M). \\
 \diamond L @ \diamond M &= \left[\left\langle \left(\frac{1 - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q + 1 - \delta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q}, \left(\frac{\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right] = \diamond (L @ M).
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $\square L \circledast \square M = \square(L \circledast M) \leq \diamond L \circledast \diamond M = \diamond(L \circledast M)$.

$$(iii) \square L \# \square M = \left[\left\langle \frac{(2)^{1/q} \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}}}{(\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q)^{1/q}}, \frac{(2)^{1/q} (1 - \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q)^{1/q} (1 - \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q)^{1/q}}{(1 - \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + 1 - \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q)^{1/q}} \right\rangle \right] \leq \square(L \# M).$$

$$\diamond L \# \diamond M = \left[\left\langle \frac{(2)^{1/q} (1 - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q)^{1/q} (1 - \delta_{m_{ij}}^q)^{1/q}}{(1 - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q + 1 - \delta_{m_{ij}}^q)^{1/q}}, \frac{(2)^{1/q} \delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}}}{(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q)^{1/q}} \right\rangle \right] \leq \diamond(L \# M).$$

Hence, $\square(L \# M) \leq \square L \# \square M \leq \diamond L \# \diamond M \leq \diamond(L \# M)$. □

The following theorems are obvious.

Theorem 3.2. For $L, M \in F_{m \times n}$,

(i) $\square [(\diamond L \circledast \diamond M)^C] = [\diamond(L \circledast M)]^C$;

(ii) $\diamond [(\square L \circledast \square M)^C] = [\square(L \circledast M)]^C$;

(iii) $\square [(\diamond L \$ \diamond M)^C] = [\diamond(L \$ M)]^C$;

(vi) $\diamond [(\square L \$ \square M)^C] = [\square(L \$ M)]^C$;

(v) $\square [(\diamond L \# \diamond M)^C] = [\diamond(L \# M)]^C$;

(vi) $\diamond [(\square L \# \square M)^C] = [\square(L \# M)]^C$;

(vii) $\square [(\diamond L * \diamond M)^C] = [\diamond(L * M)]^C$;

(viii) $\diamond [(\square L * \square M)^C] = [\square(L * M)]^C$.

Theorem 3.3. For $L, M \in F_{m \times n}$,

(i) $[(\square L \boxplus_q \diamond M)^C \circledast ((\square L)^C \boxtimes_q \diamond M)] \vee (\square L)^C = (\square L)^C$;

(ii) $[(\square L \boxtimes_q \diamond M)^C \circledast ((\square L)^C \boxplus_q \diamond M)] \wedge (\square L)^C = (\square L)^C$;

(iii) $[(\square L \boxplus_q \diamond M)^C \$ ((\square L)^C \boxtimes_q \diamond M)] \vee (\square L)^C = (\square L)^C$;

(iv) $[(\square L \boxtimes_q \diamond M)^C \$ ((\square L)^C \boxplus_q \diamond M)] \wedge (\square L)^C = (\square L)^C$;

(v) $[(\square L \boxplus_q \diamond M)^C \# ((\square L)^C \boxtimes_q \diamond M)] \vee (\square L)^C = (\square L)^C$;

(vi) $[(\square L \boxtimes_q \diamond M)^C \# ((\square L)^C \boxplus_q \diamond M)] \wedge (\square L)^C = (\square L)^C$;

(vii) $[(\diamond L \boxplus_q \square M)^C \circledast ((\square L)^C \boxtimes_q \diamond M)] \vee (\diamond L)^C = (\diamond L)^C$;

(viii) $[(\diamond L \boxplus_q \square M)^C \$ ((\square L)^C \boxtimes_q \diamond M)] \vee (\diamond L)^C = (\diamond L)^C$;

(ix) $[(\diamond L \boxtimes_q \square M)^C \# ((\square L)^C \boxplus_q \diamond M)] \vee (\diamond L)^C = (\diamond L)^C$;

(x) $[(\diamond L \boxplus_q \square M)^C \circledast ((\diamond L)^C \boxtimes_q \square M)] \vee (\diamond L)^C = (\diamond L)^C$;

$$(xi) \quad \left[(\diamond L \boxplus_q \square M)^C \$((\diamond L)^C \boxtimes_q \square M) \right] \vee (\diamond L)^C = (\diamond L);$$

$$(xii) \quad \left[(\diamond L \boxplus_q \square M)^C \#((\diamond L)^C \boxtimes_q \square M) \right] \vee (\diamond L)^C = (\diamond L).$$

In the next section, we state and prove some new results involving implication operator with other q-ROFM operations

4. Some results of q-ROFM based on implication operator

In this section, the proofs of the following theorems and corollaries follows from the Definitions 2.1, and Lemma 2.1.

Theorem 4.1. For $L, M \in F_{m \times n}$,

$$(i) \quad (L^C \rightarrow M) @ (L \rightarrow M^C)^C = (L @ M);$$

$$(ii) \quad (L^C \rightarrow M) \boxplus_q (L \rightarrow M^C)^C = (L \boxplus_q M);$$

$$(iii) \quad (L^C \rightarrow M) \boxtimes_q (L \rightarrow M^C)^C = (L \boxtimes_q M);$$

$$(iv) \quad (L^C \rightarrow M) \$ (L \rightarrow M^C)^C = (L \$ M);$$

$$(v) \quad (L^C \rightarrow M) \# (L \rightarrow M^C)^C = (L \# M);$$

$$(vi) \quad (L \rightarrow M)^C \boxplus_q (M \rightarrow L) = (L \boxplus_q M^C);$$

$$(vii) \quad (L \rightarrow M)^C @ (M \rightarrow L) = (L @ M^C);$$

$$(viii) \quad (L \rightarrow M)^C \boxtimes_q (M \rightarrow L) = (L \boxtimes_q M^C);$$

$$(ix) \quad (L \rightarrow M)^C \$ (M \rightarrow L) = (L \$ M^C);$$

$$(x) \quad (L \rightarrow M)^C \# (M \rightarrow L) = (L \# M^C).$$

Proof. We prove (i) and (vi), results (iii), (iv), (v), (vii), (viii), (ix), (x) can be proved analogously.

$$\begin{aligned} (i) \quad & (L^C \rightarrow B) @ (A \rightarrow M^C)^C \\ &= \left[\left(\frac{\max \{ \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q, \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q \} + \min \{ \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q, \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q \}}{2} \right)^{1/q}, \left(\frac{\min \{ \delta_{l_{ij}}^q, \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \} + \max \{ \delta_{l_{ij}}^q, \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \}}{2} \right)^{1/q} \right], \\ &= \left[\left\langle \left(\frac{\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q}, \left(\frac{\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right], \\ &= (L @ M). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} (vi) \quad & (L \rightarrow M)^C \boxplus_q (M \rightarrow L) \\ &= \left[\left(\min \{ \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q, \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \} + \max \{ \delta_{m_{ij}}^q, \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q \} - \min \{ \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q, \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \} \max \{ \delta_{m_{ij}}^q, \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q \} \right)^{1/q}, \right. \\ & \quad \left. \max \{ \delta_{l_{ij}}^q, \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q \} \min \{ \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q, \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \} \right], \\ &= \left[\left\langle \left(\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q}, \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q \right\rangle \right], \end{aligned}$$

$$= (L \boxplus_q M^C).$$

□

Theorem 4.2. For $L, M \in F_{m \times n}$,

- (i) $((L \boxplus_q M) \rightarrow (L \otimes M)^C)^C = ((L \otimes M) \rightarrow (L \boxplus_q M)^C)^C = (L \otimes M)$;
- (ii) $((L \boxplus_q M)^C \rightarrow (L \otimes M)) = ((L \otimes M)^C \rightarrow (L \boxplus_q M)) = (L \boxplus_q M)$;
- (iii) $((L \boxtimes_q M) \rightarrow (L \otimes M)^C)^C = ((L \otimes M) \rightarrow (L \boxtimes_q M)^C)^C = (L \boxtimes_q M)$;
- (iv) $((L \boxtimes_q M)^C \rightarrow (L \otimes M)) = ((L \otimes M)^C \rightarrow (L \boxtimes_q M)) = (L \otimes M)$;
- (v) $((L \boxplus_q M) \rightarrow (L \# M)^C)^C = ((L \# M) \rightarrow (L \boxplus_q M)^C)^C = (L \# M)$;
- (vi) $((L \boxplus_q M)^C \rightarrow (L \# M)) = ((L \# M)^C \rightarrow (L \boxplus_q M)) = (L \boxplus_q M)$;
- (vii) $((L \boxtimes_q M) \rightarrow (L \# M)^C)^C = ((L \# M) \rightarrow (L \boxtimes_q M)^C)^C = (L \boxtimes_q M)$;
- (viii) $((L \boxtimes_q M)^C \rightarrow (L \# M)) = ((L \# M)^C \rightarrow (L \boxtimes_q M)) = (L \# M)$;
- (ix) $((L \boxplus_q M) \rightarrow (L \$ M)^C)^C = ((L \$ M) \rightarrow (L \boxplus_q M)^C)^C = (L \$ M)$;
- (x) $((L \boxplus_q M)^C \rightarrow (L \$ M)) = ((L \$ M)^C \rightarrow (L \boxplus_q M)) = (L \boxplus_q M)$;
- (xi) $((L \boxtimes_q M) \rightarrow (L \$ M)^C)^C = ((L \$ M) \rightarrow (L \boxtimes_q M)^C)^C = (L \boxtimes_q M)$;
- (xii) $((L \boxtimes_q M)^C \rightarrow (L \$ M)) = ((L \$ M)^C \rightarrow (L \boxtimes_q M)) = (L \$ M)$;
- (xiii) $((L \boxplus_q M) \rightarrow (L \boxtimes_q M)^C)^C = ((L \boxtimes_q M) \rightarrow (L \boxplus_q M)^C)^C = (L \boxtimes_q M)$;
- (xiv) $((L \boxtimes_q M)^C \rightarrow (L \boxplus_q M)) = ((L \boxplus_q M)^C \rightarrow (L \boxtimes_q M)) = (L \boxplus_q M)$.

Proof. We prove (i), (iii), (v), (vii), (ix) and (xiii), other results can be proved analogously,

$$\begin{aligned} & (i) \quad ((L \boxplus_q M) \rightarrow (L \otimes M)^C)^C \\ &= \left[\min \left\{ \left(\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q - \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q}, \left(\frac{\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q} \right\}, \max \left\{ \delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}}, \left(\frac{\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q} \right\} \right], \\ &= \left[\left\langle \left(\frac{\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q}, \left(\frac{\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right], \\ &= A \otimes B. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & ((L \otimes M) \rightarrow (L \boxplus_q M)^C)^C \\ &= \left[\min \left\{ \left(\frac{\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q}, \left(\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q - \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q} \right\}, \max \left\{ \left(\frac{\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q}, \delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}} \right\} \right], \\ &= \left[\left\langle \left(\frac{\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q}, \left(\frac{\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right], \\ &= A \otimes B. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $((L \boxplus_q M) \rightarrow (L \otimes M)^C)^C = ((L \otimes M) \rightarrow (L \boxplus_q M)^C)^C = (L \otimes M)$.

$$(iii) \quad ((L \boxtimes_q M) \rightarrow (L \otimes M)^C)^C$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \left[\min \left\{ \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}}, \left(\frac{\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q} \right\}, \max \left\{ \left(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q}, \left(\frac{\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q} \right\} \right], \\
 &= \left[\left\langle \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}}, \left(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right], \\
 &= L \boxtimes_q M.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &((L \otimes M) \rightarrow (L \boxtimes_q M)^C)^C \\
 &= \left[\min \left\{ \left(\frac{\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q}, \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}} \right\}, \max \left\{ \left(\frac{\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q}, \left(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q} \right\} \right], \\
 &= \left[\left\langle \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}}, \left(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right], \\
 &= L \boxtimes_q M.
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $((L \boxtimes_q M) \rightarrow (L \otimes M)^C)^C = ((L \otimes M) \rightarrow (L \boxtimes_q M)^C)^C = (L \boxtimes_q M)$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 (v) \quad &((L \boxplus_q M) \rightarrow (L \# M)^C)^C \\
 &= \left[\min \left\{ \left(\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q - \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q}, \frac{(2)^{1/q} \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}}}{\left(\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q}} \right\}, \max \left\{ \delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}}, \frac{(2)^{1/q} \delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}}}{\left(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q}} \right\} \right], \\
 &= \left[\left\langle \frac{(2)^{1/q} \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}}}{\left(\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q}}, \frac{(2)^{1/q} \delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}}}{\left(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q}} \right\rangle \right], \\
 &= L \# M.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &((L \# M) \rightarrow (L \boxplus_q M)^C)^C \\
 &= \left[\min \left\{ \frac{(2)^{1/q} \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}}}{\left(\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q}}, \left(\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q - \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q} \right\}, \max \left\{ \frac{(2)^{1/q} \delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}}}{\left(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q}}, \delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}} \right\} \right], \\
 &= \left[\left\langle \frac{(2)^{1/q} \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}}}{\left(\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q}}, \frac{(2)^{1/q} \delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}}}{\left(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q}} \right\rangle \right], \\
 &= L \# M.
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $((L \boxplus_q M) \rightarrow (L \# M)^C)^C = ((L \# M) \rightarrow (L \boxplus_q M)^C)^C = (L \# M)$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 (vii) \quad &((L \boxtimes_q M) \rightarrow (L \# M)^C)^C \\
 &= \left[\min \left\{ \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}}, \frac{(2)^{1/q} \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}}}{\left(\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q}} \right\}, \max \left\{ \left(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q}, \frac{(2)^{1/q} \delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}}}{\left(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q}} \right\} \right], \\
 &= \left[\left\langle \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}}, \left(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right], \\
 &= L \boxtimes_q M.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & ((L\#M) \rightarrow (L \boxtimes_q M)^C)^C \\
 &= \left[\min \left\{ \frac{(2)^{1/q} \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}}}{(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q)^{1/q}}, \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}} \right\}, \max \left\{ \frac{(2)^{1/q} \delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}}}{(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q)^{1/q}}, (\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q)^{1/q} \right\} \right], \\
 &= \left[\left\langle \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}}, (\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right], \\
 &= L \boxtimes_q M.
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $((L \boxtimes_q M) \rightarrow (L\#M)^C)^C = ((L\#M) \rightarrow (L \boxtimes_q M)^C)^C = (L \boxtimes_q M)$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 (ix) \quad & ((L \boxplus_q M) \rightarrow (L\$M)^C)^C \\
 &= \left[\min \left\{ (\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q - \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q)^{1/q}, (\zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}})^{1/q} \right\}, \max \left\{ \delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}}, (\delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}})^{1/q} \right\} \right], \\
 &= \left[\left\langle (\zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}})^{1/q}, (\delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}})^{1/q} \right\rangle \right], \\
 &= L\$M.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & ((L\$M) \rightarrow (L \boxplus_q M)^C)^C \\
 &= \left[\min \left\{ (\zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}})^{1/q}, (\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q - \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q)^{1/q} \right\}, \max \left\{ (\delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}})^{1/q}, \delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}} \right\} \right], \\
 &= \left[\left\langle (\zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}})^{1/q}, (\delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}})^{1/q} \right\rangle \right], \\
 &= L\$M.
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $((L \boxplus_q M) \rightarrow (L\$M)^C)^C = ((L\$M) \rightarrow (L \boxplus_q M)^C)^C = (L\$M)$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 (xi) \quad & ((L \boxtimes_q M) \rightarrow (L\$M)^C)^C \\
 &= \left[\min \left\{ \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}}, (\zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}})^{1/q} \right\}, \max \left\{ (\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q)^{1/q}, (\delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}})^{1/q} \right\} \right], \\
 &= \left[\left\langle \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}}, (\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right], \\
 &= L \boxtimes_q M.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & ((L\$M) \rightarrow (L \boxtimes_q M)^C)^C \\
 &= \left[\min \left\{ (\zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}})^{1/q}, \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}} \right\}, \max \left\{ (\delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}})^{1/q}, (\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q)^{1/q} \right\} \right] \\
 &= \left[\left\langle \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}}, (\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right], \\
 &= L \boxtimes_q M.
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $((L \boxtimes_q M) \rightarrow (L\$M)^C)^C = ((L\$M) \rightarrow (L \boxtimes_q M)^C)^C = (L \boxtimes_q M)$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 (xiii) \quad & ((L \boxplus_q M) \rightarrow (L \boxtimes_q M)^C)^C \\
 &= \left[\min \left\{ (\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q - \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q)^{1/q}, \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}} \right\}, \max \left\{ \delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}}, (\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q)^{1/q} \right\} \right],
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \left[\left\langle \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}}, \left(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right], \\
 &= L \boxtimes_q M. \\
 ((L \boxtimes_q M) \rightarrow (L \boxplus_q M)^C)^C \\
 &= \left[\min \left\{ \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}}, \left(\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q - \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q} \right\}, \max \left\{ \left(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q}, \delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}} \right\} \right] \\
 &= \left[\left\langle \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}}, \left(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right], \\
 &= L \boxtimes_q M. \\
 \text{Hence, } ((L \boxplus_q M) \rightarrow (L \boxtimes_q M)^C)^C &= ((L \boxtimes M) \rightarrow (L \boxplus_q M)^C)^C = (L \boxtimes_q M). \quad \square
 \end{aligned}$$

The proof of the following Corollaries follows from Theorem 4.2.

Corollary 4.1. For $L, M \in F_{m \times n}$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 ((L \boxtimes_q M) \rightarrow (L \otimes M)^C)^C &= ((L \otimes M) \rightarrow (L \boxtimes_q M)^C)^C \\
 &= ((L \boxtimes_q M) \rightarrow (L \# M)^C)^C = ((L \# M) \rightarrow (L \boxtimes_q M)^C)^C \\
 &= ((L \boxtimes_q M) \rightarrow (L \$ M)^C)^C = ((L \$ M) \rightarrow (L \boxtimes_q M)^C)^C \\
 &= ((L \boxplus_q M) \rightarrow (L \boxtimes_q M)^C)^C = ((L \boxtimes_q M) \rightarrow (L \boxplus_q M)^C)^C \\
 &= (L \boxtimes_q M).
 \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 4.2. For $L, M \in F_{m \times n}$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 ((L \boxplus_q M)^C \rightarrow (L \otimes M)) &= ((L \otimes M)^C \rightarrow (L \boxplus_q M)) \\
 &= ((L \boxplus_q M)^C \rightarrow (L \# M)) = ((L \# M)^C \rightarrow (L \boxplus_q M)) \\
 &= ((L \boxplus_q M)^C \rightarrow (L \$ M)) = ((L \$ M)^C \rightarrow (L \boxplus_q M)) \\
 &= ((L \boxtimes_q M)^C \rightarrow (L \boxplus_q M)) = ((L \boxplus_q M)^C \rightarrow (L \boxtimes_q M)) \\
 &= (L \boxplus_q M).
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 4.3. For $L, M \in F_{m \times n}$,

$$\left[(L^C \rightarrow M) \boxplus_q (L \rightarrow M^C)^C \right] \otimes \left[(L^C \rightarrow M) \boxtimes_q (L \rightarrow M^C)^C \right] = (L \otimes M).$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \left[(L^C \rightarrow M) \boxplus_q (L \rightarrow M^C)^C \right] &= \left[\left\langle \left(\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q - \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q}, \delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}} \right\rangle \right], \\
 \left[(L^C \rightarrow M) \boxtimes_q (L \rightarrow M^C)^C \right] &= \left[\left\langle \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}}, \left(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right]. \\
 \left[(L^C \rightarrow M) \boxplus_q (L \rightarrow M^C)^C \right] \otimes \left[(L^C \rightarrow M) \boxtimes_q (L \rightarrow M^C)^C \right] \\
 &= \left(\frac{\left(\left(\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q - \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q} \right)^q + \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q}, \left(\frac{\delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q + \left(\left(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q} \right)^q}{2} \right)^{1/q}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \left[\left\langle \left(\frac{\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q}, \left(\frac{\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right] \\
 &= (L \otimes M). \quad \square
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 4.4. For $L, M \in F_{m \times n}$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\left[\left((L^C \rightarrow M) \boxplus_q (L \rightarrow M^C)^C \right) \cap \left((L^C \rightarrow M) \boxtimes_q (L \rightarrow M^C)^C \right) \right] \\
 &\circledast \left[\left((L^C \rightarrow M) \boxplus_q (L \rightarrow M^C)^C \right) \cup \left((L^C \rightarrow M) \boxtimes_q (L \rightarrow M^C)^C \right) \right] = (L \otimes M).
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\left[\left((L^C \rightarrow M) \boxplus_q (L \rightarrow M^C)^C \right) \cap \left((L^C \rightarrow M) \boxtimes_q (L \rightarrow M^C)^C \right) \right], \\
 &= \left[\min \left\{ \left(\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q - \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q}, \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}} \right\}, \max \left\{ \delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}}, \left(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q} \right\} \right], \\
 &= \left[\left\langle \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}}, \left(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right]. \\
 &\left[\left((L^C \rightarrow M) \boxplus_q (L \rightarrow M^C)^C \right) \cup \left((L^C \rightarrow M) \boxtimes_q (L \rightarrow M^C)^C \right) \right], \\
 &= \left[\max \left\{ \left(\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q - \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q}, \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}} \right\}, \min \left\{ \delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}}, \left(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q} \right\} \right], \\
 &= \left[\left\langle \left(\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q - \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q}, \delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}} \right\rangle \right]. \\
 &\left[\left((L^C \rightarrow M) \boxplus_q (L \rightarrow M^C)^C \right) \cap \left((L^C \rightarrow M) \boxtimes_q (L \rightarrow M^C)^C \right) \right] \\
 &\circledast \left[\left((L^C \rightarrow M) \boxplus_q (L \rightarrow M^C)^C \right) \cup \left((L^C \rightarrow M) \boxtimes_q (L \rightarrow M^C)^C \right) \right], \\
 &= \left[\left(\frac{\left(\left(\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q - \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q} \right)^q + \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q}, \left(\frac{\delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q + \left(\left(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q} \right)^q}{2} \right)^{1/q} \right], \\
 &= \left[\left\langle \left(\frac{\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q}, \left(\frac{\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right], \\
 &= L \otimes M. \quad \square
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 4.5. For $L, M \in F_{m \times n}$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\left[\left((L \boxplus_q M) \rightarrow (L \otimes M)^C \right)^C \cup \left((L \boxtimes_q M) \rightarrow (L \otimes M)^C \right)^C \right] \\
 &\cup \left[\left((L \boxplus_q M) \rightarrow (L \otimes M)^C \right)^C \cap \left((L \boxtimes_q M) \rightarrow (L \otimes M)^C \right)^C \right] = L \otimes M.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. From Theorem 4.2, we have

$$\left((L \boxplus_q M) \rightarrow (L \otimes M)^C \right)^C = \left[\left\langle \left(\frac{\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q}, \left(\frac{\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right],$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left((L \boxtimes_q M) \rightarrow (L \otimes M)^C \right)^C = \left[\left\langle \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}}, \left(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right] \\
 & \left[\left((L \boxplus_q M) \rightarrow (L \otimes M)^C \right)^C \cup \left((L \boxtimes_q M) \rightarrow (L \otimes M)^C \right)^C \right], \\
 & = \left[\max \left\{ \left(\frac{\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q}, (\zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}}) \right\}, \min \left\{ \left(\frac{\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q}, \left(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q} \right\} \right], \\
 & = \left[\left\langle \left(\frac{\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q}, \left(\frac{\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right], \\
 & \left[\left((L \boxplus_q M) \rightarrow (L \otimes M)^C \right)^C \cap \left((L \boxtimes_q M) \rightarrow (L \otimes M)^C \right)^C \right], \\
 & = \left[\min \left\{ \left(\frac{\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q}, (\zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}}) \right\}, \max \left\{ \left(\frac{\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q}, \left(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q} \right\} \right], \\
 & = \left[\left\langle \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}}, \left(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right].
 \end{aligned}$$

Now we consider,

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left[\left((L \boxplus_q M) \rightarrow (L \otimes M)^C \right)^C \cup \left((L \boxtimes_q M) \rightarrow (L \otimes M)^C \right)^C \right] \\
 & \cup \left[\left((L \boxplus_q M) \rightarrow (L \otimes M)^C \right)^C \cap \left((L \boxtimes_q M) \rightarrow (L \otimes M)^C \right)^C \right], \\
 & = \left[\max \left\{ \left(\frac{\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q}, (\zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}}) \right\}, \min \left\{ \left(\frac{\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q}, \left(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q} \right\} \right], \\
 & = \left[\left\langle \left(\frac{\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q}, \left(\frac{\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right], \\
 & = L \otimes M. \quad \square
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 4.6. For $L, M \in F_{m \times n}$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left[\left((L \boxplus_q M) \rightarrow (L \otimes M)^C \right)^C \cup \left((L \boxtimes_q M) \rightarrow (L \otimes M)^C \right)^C \right] \\
 & \cap \left[\left((L \boxplus_q M) \rightarrow (L \otimes M)^C \right)^C \cap \left((L \boxtimes_q M) \rightarrow (L \otimes M)^C \right)^C \right] = L \boxtimes_q M.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. The proof is similar to that of Theorem 4.5. □

Theorem 4.7. For $L, M \in F_{m \times n}$,

$$\left((L \boxplus_q M)^C \rightarrow (L \otimes M) \right) \otimes \left((L \boxtimes_q M) \rightarrow (L \otimes M)^C \right) = (L \otimes M).$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Proof.} \quad & \left((L \boxplus_q M)^C \rightarrow (L \otimes M) \right) = \left[\left\langle \left(\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q - \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q}, \delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}} \right\rangle \right], \\
 & \left((L \boxtimes_q M) \rightarrow (L \otimes M)^C \right)^C = \left[\left\langle \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}}, \left(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right].
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & ((L \boxplus_q M)^C \rightarrow (L \otimes M)) \otimes ((L \boxtimes_q M) \rightarrow (L \otimes M)^C)^C \\
 &= \left[\left(\frac{\left(\left(\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q - \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q} \right)^q + (\zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}})^q}{2} \right)^{1/q}, \left(\frac{(\delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}})^q + \left(\left(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q} \right)^q}{2} \right)^{1/q} \right], \\
 &= \left[\left\langle \left(\frac{\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q}, \left(\frac{\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right], \\
 &= L \otimes M. \quad \square
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 4.8. For $L, M \in F_{m \times n}$,

$$((L \boxplus_q M)^C \rightarrow (L \# M)) \otimes ((L \boxtimes_q M) \rightarrow (L \# M)^C)^C = (L \otimes M).$$

$$\text{Proof. } ((L \boxplus_q M)^C \rightarrow (L \# M)) = \left[\left\langle \left(\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q - \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q}, \delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}} \right\rangle \right],$$

$$((L \boxtimes_q M) \rightarrow (L \# M)^C)^C = \left[\left\langle \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}}, \left(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right].$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & ((L \boxplus_q M)^C \rightarrow (L \# M)) \otimes ((L \boxtimes_q M) \rightarrow (L \# M)^C)^C \\
 &= \left[\left(\frac{\left(\left(\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q - \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q} \right)^q + (\zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}})^q}{2} \right)^{1/q}, \left(\frac{(\delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}})^q + \left(\left(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q} \right)^q}{2} \right)^{1/q} \right], \\
 &= \left[\left\langle \left(\frac{\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q}, \left(\frac{\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right], \\
 &= L \otimes M. \quad \square
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 4.9. For $L, M \in F_{m \times n}$,

$$((L \boxplus_q M)^C \rightarrow (L \$ M)) \otimes ((L \boxtimes_q M) \rightarrow (L \$ M)^C)^C = (L \otimes M).$$

$$\text{Proof. } ((L \boxplus_q M)^C \rightarrow (L \$ M)) = \left[\left\langle \left(\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q - \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q}, \delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}} \right\rangle \right],$$

$$((L \boxtimes_q M) \rightarrow (L \$ M)^C)^C = \left[\left\langle \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}}, \left(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right].$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & ((L \boxplus_q M)^C \rightarrow (L \$ M)) \otimes ((L \boxtimes_q M) \rightarrow (L \$ M)^C)^C \\
 &= \left[\left(\frac{\left(\left(\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q - \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q} \right)^q + (\zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}})^q}{2} \right)^{1/q}, \left(\frac{(\delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}})^q + \left(\left(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q} \right)^q}{2} \right)^{1/q} \right], \\
 &= \left[\left\langle \left(\frac{\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q}, \left(\frac{\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right], \\
 &= L \otimes M. \quad \square
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 4.10. For $L, M \in F_{m \times n}$,

$$((L \boxtimes_q M)^C \rightarrow (L \boxplus_q M)) \textcircled{\text{}} ((L \boxplus_q M) \rightarrow (L \boxtimes_q M)^C)^C = (L \textcircled{\text{}} M)$$

Proof. $((L \boxtimes_q M)^C \rightarrow (L \boxplus_q M)) = \left[\left\langle \left(\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q - \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q}, \delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}} \right\rangle \right],$

$$((L \boxplus_q M) \rightarrow (L \boxtimes_q M)^C)^C = \left[\left\langle \zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}}, \left(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right].$$

$$\begin{aligned} & ((L \boxtimes_q M)^C \rightarrow (L \boxplus_q M)) \textcircled{\text{}} ((L \boxplus_q M) \rightarrow (L \boxtimes_q M)^C)^C \\ &= \left[\left(\frac{\left(\left(\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q - \zeta_{l_{ij}}^q \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q} \right)^q + \left(\zeta_{l_{ij}} \zeta_{m_{ij}} \right)^q}{2} \right)^{1/q}, \left(\frac{\left(\delta_{l_{ij}} \delta_{m_{ij}} \right)^q + \left(\left(\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q - \delta_{l_{ij}}^q \delta_{m_{ij}}^q \right)^{1/q} \right)^q}{2} \right)^{1/q} \right], \\ &= \left[\left\langle \left(\frac{\zeta_{l_{ij}}^q + \zeta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q}, \left(\frac{\delta_{l_{ij}}^q + \delta_{m_{ij}}^q}{2} \right)^{1/q} \right\rangle \right], \\ &= L \textcircled{\text{}} M. \quad \square \end{aligned}$$

5. Conclusion and future scope

More importantly, in this paper we have proposed some new operations $[\$, \#, *, \rightarrow]$ for q-ROFM and discussed many interesting properties not limit to novel operations $(\boxplus_q, \boxtimes_q, \textcircled{\text{}}, \square, \diamond, \cap, \cup)$, which can enrich the operation theory. Further we proved necessity and possibility operations of q-rung orthopair fuzzy matrices. Finally, we have identified and proved several of these properties, particularly those involving the operator $L \rightarrow M$ defined as q-rung orthopair fuzzy implication with other operations. Our study prompts for further properties as also for defining possibly new operations. Thus there remains scope for studying more properties of these matrices arising from those other defining set operations that may be thought of using other ways of combining the functions ζ, δ . In further research, we may apply these operations in the field of different areas, for example, dynamic decision and consensus, business and marketing management, design, engineering and manufacturing, information technology and networking applications, human resources management, military applications, energy management, geographic information system applications etc.

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